

Research

Language Policy: Rethinking Positional of Frenchification and Malgachisation as Educational Challenges in Madagascar After the 1972 Madagascar Crisis

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Abstract: This study investigates the challenges and impacts of linguistic and bilingual dualism in Madagascar. It was coupled with these three objectives (1) to find out the context of bilinguals before and after colonization; (2) to expose the impacts of language policy and practice in Madagascar's education field; (3) to examine the current situation of linguistic dualism in Madagascar. This study was drafted with qualitative design and purposively interviewed three professors from three Madagascar public universities. In addition, an empirical understanding and reviews of relevant documents were used to support the study's realization. The data collected during the interview were analyzed, interpreted, and coded according to similarities and dissimilarities of their responses. The Franco-phobic, broken French and Malagasy, and delay in development significantly impacted after the 1972 Madagascar crisis. In 2019, 97% of Malagasy children under ten could not read and write. Many young people of working age would not have the required language skills even if they have spent many years studying multilanguage during their academic schooling. Therefore, the Frenchification and Malgachisation implementation in education in Madagascar had never fully realized and unbalanced its utilization. This study mainly relies on interviewing three professors that experienced the 1972 crises in Madagascar. The interviewees freely expressed their knowledge, points of view, and emotions on this particular situation in Madagascar. Therefore, it helps the government to re-think more on the matter of language policy after the dilemma of Frenchification and Malgachization as dualism linguistics in the educational system and bilingualism. The research significantly encourages the government to put and prioritize the national language at the forefront, which also means recognition and valorization of own identity.

Keywords: Madagascar, Frenchification, Malgachisation, Language Policy, Language Variaminanana

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Accepted: 16 March, 2024; **Published:** 26 March, 2024

How to cite this article: Njaratiana Mario Arthur Velo, Jocelyne Zafitsara, Brunex Arthur Velo, Antony Fute (2024). Language Policy: Rethinking Positional of Frenchification and Malgachisation as Educational Challenges in Madagascar After the 1972 Madagascar Crisis. *North American Academic Research*, 7(3), 111-126. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10969059>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Language is a tool people use to communicate between two persons, in a society, community, country and with other countries. A country may have one or two or more languages (monolingualism, bilingualism, or multilingualism) as a result of the policies that their government put. Each country has made considerable efforts to be able to control the language used by its nation, and sometimes a nation faces problems of multilingualism [1]. Society defines language as a means of developing the ability to communicate and promote personal development. Indeed, language becomes fundamental for advancing nationalized or internationalized economies [2]. The strength of a language depends on the number of people or countries that use it. For example, English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. And this strength of its use has a significant impact on the progress of the country that owns the word and substantially affects other countries either politically, economically, or socially.

However, language in a territory serves two primary functions, and it can be an informational function (including education) and a symbolic function [3]. Therefore, language must have its policy and its implementation; empirically, language policy is prone to be designed to respond to emerging issues related to multilingualism. Any country has ever been spared issues in implementing the linguistic policy. When it comes to teaching, language play is very significant because it is the first tool for students to see and know what is happening and what is development meaning. The most common thing in developing countries is that almost all languages used by their colonizers are still used today in their country, such as English, French, Portuguese, Arabic, etc.

In Africa, in particular, it can be said that there is two dominant languages vehicle on the continent, French and English. The northern and western parts of Africa mostly speak French, while the eastern and southern parts use English. In the North-West part of Africa, the French language has a considerable influence, 32 countries use French as their mother language except for Ghana, Nigeria, and the Gambia [4]. In contrast, in the eastern part of Africa, only one French-speaking country exists, Madagascar. Historically, during the kingdom time in Madagascar, Madagascar was not a French colony [5]. They cooperated closely with the United Kingdom because of the massive influence of English culture in south-eastern Africa [6]. Because of political and geopolitical reasons and unknown, non-plausible factors, Madagascar became a French colony. Indeed, from the colonization era until the present, the first and most destructive weapon of culture still haunts and scares Madagascar, which is "Frenchification (francization)" phenomenon. After colonization, the French remain in the daily life of people.

However, since the elites and university students felt that we had lost our Malagasy sovereignty entirely, that is, the Malagasy language, which first made the identity of Madagascar and made Madagascar into Madagascar, they went on a significant strike in 1972. Therefore, the term Malgachization emerged and the Malgachization phenomenon became polemic after the strike and crises of 1972. The 1972 strike and crisis in Madagascar was aimed to change entirely the educational system and curriculum into Malagasy language [7]. Madagascar has its own cultural language, Malagasy. Madagascar has an enormous advantage by having a sole national language [8], Still, the polemic generated by these two phenomena of Frenchification and Malgachisation is one of the biggest educational challenges in Madagascar and led Madagascar into a bilingualism system and a dualist linguistic. Indeed, because of the 1972 strike failure, bilingualism posed a considerable challenge to the education system. Thereat, the French language is mainly used as an administrative and educational language, i.e., it is no longer used as a typical communication vehicle for people from different regions. This problem cannot be solved yet because what is happening in Madagascar' education currently is that there are schools that use the French language entirely. Some schools mix their teaching in French and Malagasy, and some schools give particular importance to the Malagasy language. As it turns out, private schools have a better

command of the French language. In contrast, students in public schools are almost a bit difficult to use the French language for many reasons.

Statement of problem

In Madagascar, language is an eminently political subject, and language policies are often closely linked to the regime's ideology but not necessarily to the realities of the use of language by the population. According to General Gallieni's discourse, in 1896, Madagascar has today become a French land. Subsequently, the French language must become the basis of teaching in all the schools on the island [9]. At the first, the issues of bilingualism were caused by the ecclesiastical influence before and after the colonization era and after. This ecclesiastical influence has left scars on Madagascar educational policy and mostly its current language policy. The Christian religion is marked by the activities of missionaries and has indeed stripped Malagasy culture by proselytizing purposes. The effect of ecclesiastical influence further hardened the misdeeds of colonization on the Malagasy language and education [10]. This influence aimed to train executives who could defend, collaborate and transmit the values of the culture and West civilization, especially the Europeans. Therefore, the acculturation system was put in place in Madagascar because of the influence of Christian and religious activities.

However, since then, the Malagasy and French languages have been in a battle and an ongoing competition in education and daily life until today. By assumption, because of the vague uses and unmerciful use of the French language, the phenomenon of *frangasy* or *variaminana* has appeared. This phenomenon is the mixture of Malagasy and French side by side. According to the International organization of Francophonie, "over 4 million Malagasy people speak French, with 5% considered fully Francophone and another percent considered partially francophone"[11].

Theoretical framework

This study can refer to the balanced and unbalanced theory of bilingualism; the first theory refers to "a person who has proficiency in two languages to the extent that his or her skills for each language match those of a native speaker." In contrast, the unbalanced theory of bilingualism refers to "a person who speaks two languages but is more proficient in one than in the other." This theory is more frequent to be an unbalanced bilingual person than its balanced counterpart. Historically, this theory was used to analyze kids on using and studying two languages at the same time [12], [13].

As practice, this theory expects people to may or may not speak or master well both languages equally well. Or in contrast, may mix both languages when using them to talk to each other. Indeed, if this theory was used for kids, so it can also be applied to a country. As a weakness, the balance theory is not backed up by evidence and has shown that acquiring skills in one language can affect the learning of subsequent languages. It was identified on the false speculation that the effect of increasing the additional language can draw away a decrease in the first language.

After an empirical reflection by analyzing the number of populations in Madagascar and the International organization of Francophonie statement, a hypothesis can be affirmed that Madagascar faced an unbalanced than balanced bilingual, which is that the Malagasy were more proficiently mastered than the French.

Research objectives

- 1) To find out the context of bilingual before and after colonization
- 2) To expose the impacts of language policy and practice in Madagascar' education field
- 3) To examine the current situation of linguistic dualism in Madagascar

Method

This study highlights the challenges of the linguistic and bilingual dualism in Madagascar's educational field after the 1972 political crisis in Madagascar. The study interviews three professors from three public universities. Professors are the purposively chosen as they know more about the complex issues that Madagascar had passed through with political crises, especially the 1972 Madagascar crisis. As to respect the nature of qualitative method, respondents' responses are codified for protecting their information confidentiality and personality. Therefore, the responses are presented as follows: (Pr3) ...; (Pr2;3;1). This study is as well supported by several academics' research, linguistic policy, *Malgachisation*, and *Frenchification* documents that many researchers and learners have used concerning this particular research topic. The researchers likewise consider empirical understanding and knowledge when analyzing the results.

Findings

History of the Malagasy language

Historically, the Malagasy language was taken from the Austronesian family of languages due to the smooth migration from the Asian continent to Madagascar, such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, and Arabia, about 400–700 AD [14]. Most immigrants who arrived by boat in Madagascar at that period were sailors. Those immigrants were known as the proto-Malagasy, which had a strong relationship with some African Bantu (Bantu-people) that had built some Malagasy words into the Malagasy language. The Malagasy alphabet contains 21 English letters; consequence, C, Q, U, W, and X are not included. 93% of the Malagasy vocabulary is Malayo-Polynesian, and most of the words used in animal husbandry are almost related to Bantu origins [15]. Some mixt loanwords from Bantu-substratum [16], Arabic, and Islamism (around the 12th century) were discovered in the old Malagasy language. The locals were influenced and inspired by this circumstance, whether in their religion or their first manuscripts were written in Malagasy. That was strongly found from the North-East to South-East coast and still exists by the Antaimoro tribe situated around Manakara-Vohipeno in the southeast part of the island [17]. At that time, the manuscript was called Antemoro-scribes. Respondents Pr3 and Pr1 affirmed that,

“As for the Malagasy language, it is evident that we live completely in the language of other people from Asia, and there are many foreigners who admit and still affirm that the Malagasy language is full of Asian vocabulary, that is, Malaysian-Indonesian. Sometimes they will say that the Malagasy are not fully African.”

In 1657 in Tolagnaro, known as fort-dauphin, there was found the first texts written in Malagasy by Catholic missionaries used Latin characters [18]. During the kingdom of Radama I, king of the Merina tribe, in 1818, the British missionaries introduced most of the modern writing of Malagasy with Latin characters. Before, the Antaimoro-scribes based on Arabic script was used only for local rituals and for virtual and magical goals in society. In this era, the king had already known particular French words, certainly French dialectal, and he had categorically persuaded that the Latin alphabet should be adopted to make writing accessible to disciplines and be an instructional language. The king Radama I decided that French vowels and English consonants should be chosen on one letter for each sound [19]. Those British missionaries had primarily started their missions by translating the Bible to introduce Christianity into the country and begin a course of reading and writing [20]. Indeed, the first school was the missionary school, using the Malagasy language was automatically the instructional language recommended by the king, mainly using borrowed words from European and English languages [21]. The respondents have stated that

“The presence of foreigners such as the English and French in Madagascar flourished before the colonial period. The Malagasy language became mixed even though the Malagasy did not have writing in the Malagasy language

and there are even some words that will no longer be free such as “cuillère” which Malagasy in the east call “koera” which means spoon in official Malagasy.”

The table 1 represents the list of some English and French words used by people in the eastern part of Madagascar, especially the tribe of Betsimisaraka and Antakarana.

<i>English</i>	<i>Malagasy</i>
Bible	Baiboly
Tar	Tara
English	Angilisy
<i>French</i>	<i>Malagasy</i>
Cuillère	Koera/sotro
La Bougie	Labozia
La Table	Latabatra

Source: Author's findings, 2022

Educational context of Malgachisation

Malgachisation serves to harmonize the education content and methods with the revolution imperative or the rulers or decision-makers imperative. By definition, “Malgachisation” refers to the period when education in Madagascar switched from French to a more Malagasy track (Voarintsoa et al., 2019). Yet, it was a linguistic and educational policy taking the form of a set of political and cultural provisions intended to promote the Malagasy language and identity [22]. The British missionaries brought the first education to Madagascar, mainly characterized by a western form of education in the 1820s. In 1867, Norwegian missionaries started their educational work in Madagascar. Historically, the Merina aristocracy and its supremacy, most of them converted into Christianity, particularly Protestantism, which has ruled over a vast and enormous part of Madagascar; that regime introduced the western missionaries to Madagascar [23].

Malgachisation policy was applied for a short period before the French colonization. In 1835, literacy spread through schools; missionaries and students were estimated at 15,000. The qualification was persons who knew how to read and write the new Malagasy language. Despite significant issues and political distortion during the reign of Queen Ranaivalona I, the missionary school system and the Malgachisation into Protestant and Roman Catholic institutions continued to blow and grow. Malgachisation was strongly popular during the Anarchy regime in Madagascar [24]. However, despite the Malagasy language being the language of instruction in most Madagascar schools before the French colonization in 1897, during colonization, however, all schools that did not use French for educational instruction were shut down [19].

Frenchification of the educational context

From 1896 to 1960, Madagascar became a French colony; it was a period when the language of instruction was French to distance the national population from its cultural roots; it was the period of “Frenchification.” Research affirmed that the advantage of having one national language is a benefit for the country compared to the multitude of languages in most other African countries [25]. Conversely, Madagascar preferred to reject the gain of this unique linguistic situation. “Frenchification” refers to when education in Madagascar re-switched from Malagasy to French, and was a linguistic and educational policy taking the form of a set of political provisions intended to promote the French language.

During the colonial era, the colonizers adopted a system of public schools divided into two. Firstly, elite schools were established for the children of French citizens, unlikely a status few Malagasy enjoyed and had a right to register. Secondly, indigenous schools for Malagasy provided practical and professional training but were not designed to instruct students for managerial or responsible positions. The Frenchification policy was considered dedicated only to privileged people, such as wealthy families and high officials [26]. After World War II, reforms to the public school system were put in place to provide more educational opportunities for Malagasy people. Thus, after its independence, in 1960, Madagascar had referred identically to France in the system of education [27]; then, the ruling elite of the capital and other urban centers have continuously used French as the language of administration, and some minorities even adopted French as their everyday family language.

Current Frenchification and Malgachisation

In 2007, the government persuaded Malagasy and French language policy to be considered the official languages of Madagascar [28]. According to Article 6 of the Draft Constitution, September 2010, "Malagasy is the national language," with some variation of the language spoken by 77 percent of the citizens [29]. In 2008, Malagasy Madagascar again made an amendment and reviewed its language policy; indeed, "the Malagasy language will be the means of instruction for primary education while French as a second language will be reinforced" [30]. This revision was incited by the incapacity of many graduates of the primary school system to function in a system that utilized French as the medium of instruction, and the secondary level exam is only in French. In 2009, however, national political disturbance brought this policy discussion to a cessation; indeed, that caused little progress has been made towards its implementation [27].

The Francophonie High Council estimated that in 2003, "0.57% of the Malagasy use French exclusively, 15.82% use French sometimes, while 83.61% use only Malagasy" [31]. After these statistics, French remains the dominating academic language and stays the administrative language. In Madagascar, the French language remains the force of social mobility; consequently, wealthy families, including politicians, massively sent their children to French-speaking schools to ensure future jobs and ability. That phenomenon influenced poor families to put effort into saving money to afford their children a better education and purpose to a better future for them. Since 2007, the school curriculum has been revised, especially for primary school, and called for assembling lessons around disciplines including Malagasy, English, and French [32]. The Malagasy language is used as the instructional language from the first three to the first five grades; in grade one, French would be taught as a subject, and English would be started and introduced in Grade 4.

Impacts of language policy and practice in Madagascar

Indirect Francophobic

The impact of the political coup always had its repercussion and destabilized the education system in Madagascar. During the socialist revolution in the second republic in 1972, a protestation was provoking division in the relationship between languages and schools. This protestation of students put an end to the first republic in this country by writing and posting on most angles of the street the "French language of slaves." Students felt that using the French language as an education language meant a return to slavery, royalty, and feudalism; it was hard to manage that protestation. Accordingly, a Francophobic wind blew everywhere. Indeed, Socialism, Marxism, and Leninism became popular topics and a theme of disciplines in primary and secondary schools. During this period, Malgachization in education obtained its legal status issues in the official bulletin of the Ministry of National Education and Culture (MENAC) numbers 10 and 11 of 02.15.1973. This process of Malgachization finally resulted in the promulgation of law 78-040 of 08/17/1978; it was about an educational and linguistic overhaul. Hence, in Madagascar, the process of Frenchization to Malgachization policy due to the socialist revolution had provoked the French language into the status of a foreign language. Respondents Pr2 and Pr1 criticized that

"The continued use of the French language after independence in 1960 caused hostility between the Malagasy and the French. One of the primary purposes of the 1972 strikes was to completely change the school system to the Malagasy language and make it suitable for the current situation in Madagascar. Unfortunately, it cannot be established and accepted because of unknown and obscure reasons."

Dethronement of Malgachization policy

In Madagascar, each political crisis has infected and changed educational policy. Since its independence in 1960, France has never totally left this country and continues to occupy especially the education sector. The communicative skills in French and Malagasy left huge gaps after ten years of incertitude adventure of Malgachization because it had invoked setbacks and disappointment. The return of using the French is considered a life jacket to re-establish back the mess of language policy and educational challenges. The decision number promulgation 1001- 00 MINESEB of 01.10.1990 by the government calls all teachers, from primary to tertiary level, to use the French language as the language of instruction for scientific subjects, history, and geography. To support bilingualism, the French government massively returned with other projects like the Madagascar School of Success or Partnership for schools in Madagascar.

Presently, educational programs, activities, school equipment, even the instructional language, etc., are all in the French language. Nonetheless, not mastered as nearly all teachers from primary education do not adequately master the teaching language due to the lack of teacher training, lack of supervision, and/or monitoring. Most teachers lack self-motivation to progress as the concerned ministry/government barely pays attention to their professional development; small wages. The learners' level decreased compared to the decade era due to the non-mastered system of instruction, which highly impacts students' level from primary to a higher level (tertiary education). In 2009, Madagascar's education field suffered significant setbacks due to the unconstitutional government takeover. This crisis set many reforms on hold, but Malagasy remained the language of instruction in the early primary grades; French was the medium of instruction. All secondary exams are in French [27]. Therefore, Malgachisation to Frenchisation was vigorous due to the political destabilization that engendered the national education system.

Broken French and Malagasy "variaminanana or frangasy"

The "variaminanana or frangasy" is the most linguistic consequence of the coexistence of French and Malagasy. Today's generation in Madagascar is deluged by the mixed practice of language practices, "variaminanana" of the French and Malagasy languages. The qualifications and performance of Malagasy students have been declining since the crisis of 1972 in Madagascar. The population has become less fluent in French and Malagasy; indeed, the number of young people fluent in French is declining. Respondents asserted that

"This mixing of languages is seen in the students' exams when we judge it because there are words that the students don't know how to write or what they mean in absolute Malagasy. Consequently, they will do it according to what they know, which reconfirms the existence of variaminana in the use of Malagasy and French by the students. The use of "variaminanana" words is not only found in teaching but can also be seen in electronic media such as email, messenger, and Facebook, among others. And many parents complain that they don't know what their children write when they send messages on their cellphones because of the use of slang words, abbreviations, words created by young people, and especially the lack of mastery of the two languages."

French is one of the two official languages of Madagascar and, in particular, the language of offices, administrative procedures, and higher education. However, as respondents affirmed, it is only mastered by a small part of the population. Consequently, Malagasy remains the most widely used language in the daily life of the communities, and French still occupies that of procedures, and scholars of higher education. Respondents anticipated that

“The use and mastery of French is an excellent sign of social success and serve as a great tool to achieve this what in life, especially with high probability. In contrast, the strength of the practice of variaminanana can prevent the majority of Malagasy people from progressing socially, especially in terms of education and getting out of poverty.”

Culturally, linguistic interbreeding is considered a "great danger" for the Malagasy language because it destroys linguistic purity and causes linguistic acculturation. Therefore, over time, the owners will no longer be able to master or use their formal maternal language. As respondents Pr1; Pr2; Pr3 have agreed,

“...Malagasy’s revaluation must be challenged to destroy the mode of perception, the ominous image, and the negativity of opinions that many Malagasy people think. The Malagasy must also believe that their language is a language of prestige, modernity, and knowledge. At the same time, its use is strongly linked to the meaning of its valuation.”

Delay in the development of research in Madagascar

Language plays a significant role in production or publication, and teaching. Many primary and secondary school teachers are classified as not fluent in French or Malagasy. This is seen in writings that are found to be full of errors; many parents complain that the things their children write are full of mistakes. While also in university, many students do not complete their studies to the end due to a lack of command of French because they are not able to write thesis and also are not able to publish. Therefore, many university professors are unable to do research due to this lack of language proficiency, especially in English. In addition, students or teachers become overwhelmed by the work and research they have to do. According to the responses obtained from the teachers, some students do not speak and do not participate in class activities for fear of mispronouncing due to not mastering the French language in particular. According to all respondents,

“One thing that does not improve research in Madagascar is the lack of mastery of foreign languages; some teachers and students are unable to do research in foreign languages. Fear of not being able to master the language is one of the reasons that delay young people from entering the teaching profession. In particular, the lack of English language skills is the main obstacle that makes some teachers not publish because they say that most of the good and high-quality publication journals are in English, so the existence of this English language also slows them down.”

The impacts of language policy can also be seen in the research productivity because the ranking might be caused by the struggle that occurred while they did publications in English.

This table below shows Madagascar ranking in research and data on the number of scientific papers published in all subject areas worldwide provided by scimago journal between 1996-2021. It is seen that Madagascar is considered less productive in research compared to its fellow country because it is ranked 124th around the world and 25th in Africa.

Table 2: Madagascar’ ranking on all research subject areas in the world and Africa

All subject areas, 1996-2021						
In the world ranking	Documents	Citable documents	Citations	Self-Citations	Citation per documents	H-index
124th	5820	5489	100776	14602	17.32	113
In Africa ranking	Documents	Citable documents	Citations	Self-Citations	Citation per documents	H-index
25th	5820	5489	100776	14602	17.32	113

Source: <https://www.scimagojr.com/countryrank.php?region=Africa> Scimago journal and country rank, 2021

Current situation language policy in Madagascar

The French language use, the need for teachers to transmit education to the students, is estimated that only about 18% of Madagascar’s primary school teachers know French adequately [33]. Furthermore, the Malagasy curriculum is focused on French grammar. Teaching often underlines memorizing over understanding, with students copying information into exercise books and memorizing these notes for exams [34]; but not learning enough French to converse or understand what they are being taught [19]. Consequently, this phenomenon led to a decrease in student’s learning, particularly in science and mathematics courses which gradually generated the ratio of grade repetition and dropout [35]. However, the Merina dialect of Malagasy is spoken in Madagascar as the Official language of Malagasy [36], by policymakers and in official communications about health, education, and daily life [37]. Contrarily, the average intelligibility of official Malagasy varies in some non-urban zones by around 70 %.

The official Malagasy language has strongly posed as a language different from the dialects spoken in the southern part of the country [33]. Therefore, Bouwer 2008 stated that “the exclusive use of Official Malagasy in education and government communications may be ineffective for much of the country.” Furthermore, the zones that use fluently Official Malagasy language have significant literacy rates and the highest levels of education [8]. The consideration of all regions outside the capital of Madagascar must be required the same treatment of equality to conquer the development of education in local areas [38].

Source: Author’s findings, 2022

Figure 1: Representation of Teachers ‘choice between two languages

Source: Author's findings, 2022

Figure 2: Representation of students' choice between two languages

These two figures above show teachers and students' choices on the instructional language preferences of which students were randomly questioned to know what they had in their minds about the use of Malagasy and French languages. And it was also done by 10 students to balance the number of teachers included in the purposive sampling. If we compare the answers and the average scores of the survey conducted with students and teachers, about the question: what would you like to use to teach, and whom would you like to use if you were to take it to school? The result showed that 60% of the students answered that they prefer the French language to be used in school, while 40% favor returning to the Malagasy language. However, the teachers answered the opposite because 10% favor returning to teaching in Malagasy while only 90% rejected it and wanted to continue to educate in French.

Approved French primary and secondary schools in Madagascar

Language policy provokes numerous dimensions, such as social differentiation or class inequality. This challenge of educational language policy has often been at the center of political debate. In Madagascar, academic credentials mainly provide opportunities to obtain employment in the government and the private sector. The distribution of educational resources is continually a vast issue with explosive political ramifications.

Historically, the system has always been marked by an unequal distribution of education resources among the country's different regions. It is proved that in the early nineteenth century, the areas of Tananarive (capital of Madagascar) and Betsileo had a long and mature history of formal education [39]. These areas concentrate most of the good opportunities for having the best schools [40] and higher educational standards than the coastal regions. That phenomenon has never been eradicated and continued to be the main factor of division in the Malagasy national life even after independence in 1960. Therefore, during and after colonization, the highland regions of Madagascar had better access to schools, which inevitably often occupied high responsibility for representing the Malagasy administration and officials' professions.

Table 3: List of 23 French schools approved by the Ministry of National Education (MEN)

City	Establishment name	Observations
Ambanja	Primary school of Charles Baudelaie	
Antalaha	French Primary school	-
Antsirabe	French Jules Verne College	-
Antsiranana	French Sadi Carnot College	-
Fianarantsoa	Rene Cassin College	-
Fort-Dauphin	French Primary school	-
Fort-Dauphin	La Claire Fontaine	High school: series ES and S
Mahajanga	French Francoise Dolto College	-
Manakara	Ecole primaire francaise	-
Mananjary	Ecole primaire francaise	-
Nosy-Be	Ecole primaire francaise Lamartine	-
Tamatave	Lycee francais deTamatave	High school: series ES, L , S and STMG
Tananarive	Colleges de France	
Tananarive	Ecole Alliance francaise, Antsahabe	High school: series ES and S
Tananarive	Ecole Bird	
Tananarive	Ecole la Clairefontaine	High school: series ES, L , S and STMG
Tananarive	Ecole Peter Pan	High school: series ES, and S
Tananarive	Ecole primaire francaise A, Ampefiloha	-
Tananarive	French Primary School B, Ampandri-anomby, and its annexe ecole primaire francaise D, Analamahitsy	-
Tananarive	French Primary School C, Ambohibo	-
Tananarive	Lycee Français	-
Tuléar	College Etienne de Flacourt	-

Source: Copyright ACTUTANA, 2021

*NB: STMG: Sciences Technology Management

ES: Economy-Science; S: Scientific; L: Literary

Although the above Table 3 represents the list of 23 French schools approved by the Malagasy government, according to empirical understanding and observation, there are many informal French schools, whether in highland regions or coastal regions, especially primary schools. That is considered the real impact of the language policy destabilization. Indeed, the creation and the establishment of private French schools in Madagascar became a source of profit and business because middle-class and poor citizens tried to afford a better education for their children in an option to choose French vocational schools. In contrast, the national private education leaders claim loud and clear that it is not a “business” and claim the status of a “public utility.” Many parents, politicians, and rich people thought that non-local languages might be the best way to learn French and English and have them as the language of instruction [41]. Indeed, for them, it is better to have a familiar language as the instruction language and to teach French or English first as a foreign language using teachers who are experts.

The effect of the implementation of language policy

Madagascar adopted the bilingual education sector characterized by official Malagasy and French schooling. In 2007, English was added in this country as a discipline for teaching [42]. The results showed that in 2019 the education service delivery indicators surveys indicate that 97% of Malagasy children under ten years old cannot read or write [43]. Many working young people would not have the required language skills even if they have spent a significant period and many years studying Multilanguage during their academic schooling. Professor Vololona Randriamarotsimba, 2020, confirmed that "the language education policy is mainly concerned with the languages taught and the languages of instruction." She supported studies carried out on plurilingualism in Europe, stating that "languages of instruction are central to education because they improve communicative skills, promote basic cognitive skills, and provide social and civic education." That is probably due to a lack of a stable educational language policy (PLE). The Ministry of National Education (MEN) has strongly envisaged the adoption and implementation of a stable PLE to map out and propose an effective solution to uplift, stabilize, and valorize Madagascar's educational situation.

Nowadays, "it is clear that mastering the mother tongue, Malagasy, and foreign languages such as English or French in schools remains a great challenge" [43]. As confirmed by the MEN, in terms of technical and vocational education in 2020, some blockages have led to this situation of inefficiency and failure. For instance, the lack of a stable language education policy in Madagascar, the lack of qualified teachers, a shortage of teaching resources printed in the local language, the lack of faith in the local language and the lack of non-mastering of instructional languages [44]. It is compulsory for Madagascar: "integrating the establishment of an Education Language Policy into the education reform seems inevitable." However, this PLE implementation cannot be done quickly without obtaining the opinions and participation of all parties concerned, such as the MEN, Technical and Vocational Education, the Government, and all public or private partnerships. It is categorically essential to establish a stable language education policy to promote better education for learners in Madagascar.

Discussions and Recommendations

During the second republic of Madagascar in the 1980s, the regime strengthened the education policy of Malagachization. However, the elite, politician children, and affluent families enrolled their children in traditional private French-language schools. Contrarily, most of the poor population had little chance to enroll in conventional French schools but registered their children progressively in public schools. All nationalistic movements aimed to renew Malagasy culture and fight for more liberty at a political level, and the colonial administration blamed the appearance of the nationalistic movements on education. In contrast, the intentions of educating the Malagasy population following the Malgachisation policy have not fulfilled the need for education, leading to these accidental consequences.

However, the educational role of the French colonial power was covered to contest Malagasy the colonizer to fight nationalism via moral and civic education. In the beginning, it was compulsory to use the local dialect; suddenly, the situation changed to the French language. Focusing on dialects and avoiding the use of the Malagasy language was part of a divide-and-rule policy used by the colonizer to fight nationalism. Indeed, the principal aim of primary education was to give children general knowledge that would be much easier if the instructional language was Malagasy. Therefore, for Madagascar, it is indisputable that the adoption and the integration of an educational language policy stable are significant to guarantee the future of Malagasy children in the coming years. It is stated that the implementation of PLE only changed after fifty years; to be well established, it needs absolute political stability whatever the various regimes changes.

Nowadays, the flourishing of French-speaking schools all over Madagascar still marks a strong presence of French culture and the acculturation of Malagasy culture. The bilingual program is adopted, but in contrast, the current educational system is not blowing because they don't speak and master the language used as an instructional language [45] which is French. Some teachers struggle, and don't master teaching in French. Malagasy children and young people

are exposed to the dilemma; consequently, they cannot master either one of the two languages, Malagasy or French. Additionally, it is also felt that the over-reliance on mixing languages makes it difficult for students to understand the lessons they are learning because they do not know the accurate translation of the word. The consequences of this phenomenon are viewed as follows: firstly, the Malagasy language is considered not valued and inferior to French. Secondly, the teachers do not receive practical training on current educational practices and bilingual education methods. Finally, it brings a high risk of dropout.

These are the three significant recommendations that should be considered for integrating the language policy in Madagascar. Malagasy and French languages should be given equal importance, and both should be used as media of instruction in primary, secondary, and higher education. This perspective might satisfy the people who are supporting both instructional languages which are Malagasy and French. In addition, to consider the sense of balanced theory of bilingualism;

- The language instructional methods should take into consideration the students' cultural background and family literacy practices; the ways of communication and expression; the individual learning styles and level of development;
- An effective language policy program should provide a stable and unique language of instruction in the children's primary language in all academic subjects while developing their proficiency in the second language.

Conclusion

This study contributes to and helps the government to rethink what measures Madagascar should take on language policy after the dilemma Frenchification (francization) and Malgachization, educational dualism linguistics, and bilingualism. Madagascar's educational problems have constantly been confronted because of the reforms resulting from unstable politics, the non-respect of the principles of equity, and equal access to education for all for decades. It is indisputable that the debates about the value and great importance of the mother tongue in the development of children can be limitless and endless. The implementation of Frenchification and Malgachisation of education in Madagascar had never fully succeeded. It has never brought significant stability and remarkable progress to Madagascar's educational system since and after the colonization. A stable and good educational language policy is fundamental to enhance and fortify teaching and learning and, more importantly, as a decisive point to determine the strength of a nation and its development contribution. Teaching and learning need to be accurate, simple, and comprehensible in favor of all participants who will easily comprehend, smooth the mutual communication and instruction content, and strengthen mutual interchange and collaboration. The country's language is the first capital resource and value it owns; it holds the key to educational development that will gradually affect the outcome of politics, economics, and society in the country. As evidence underlined, *"language is the local root of the education progression, need to be valued."* It needs to be applied from the beginning of schooling to the professional career world. However, having another language in a nation is a winning card for each individual. It is a matter of political will that Madagascar needs if it wants to choose the one and only language that Madagascar will make an official language. That's why the Malagasy ancients said, *"Andrianiko ny teniko fa ny any hafa koa feheziko"* means *I cherish my formal language and master the other foreign languages.*

In contrast, the French will always play a significant part in the life of Madagascar at all levels, specifically its citizens and instructions. Nevertheless, reshaping its system requires much effort and maturity to get more effective and productive results. A Malagasy proverb says, *"Ny hazo no vanon-ko lakana, ny tany naniriany no tsara"* which means *the tree is solid and suitable for canoes when the land where the tree has grown is fertile* [34].

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: We would like to express our gratitude to all respondents for their efforts, supports and constructive feedback in carrying out this work.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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